

MINOAS NEWSLETTERS

MINOAS key achievements of May | MINOAS Webinar | Papers submission |
Keynotes | Dissemination Milestones |

Deliverables

The two first deliverables of the MINOAS project have been completed:

- D1.1-Project handbook
- D1.2–Dissemination and Communication Plan

Milestones

The first milestone of MINOAS has been completed:

- MS1-Availability of CHILON use case definitions (M04)

Papers

The MINOAS project has already published two (2) papers:

- 1 in IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications
- 1 in IEEE Wireless Communication Letters

Keynotes

The MINOAS project has been invited to present its results in two more international conferences.

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MINOAS Webinar

Together with the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering at the University of Western Macedonia, the project MINOAS has organized a webinar with title «Stacked Intelligent Metasurfaces: Communication, Computing and Sensing in the Wave Domain». The webinar was given by Professor [Marco Di Renzo](#).

Marco Di Renzo (Fellow, IEEE) received the Laurea (cum laude) and Ph.D. degrees in electrical engineering from the University of L'Aquila, Italy, in 2003 and 2007, respectively, and the Habilitation à Diriger des Recherches (Doctor of Science) degree from University Paris-Sud (currently Paris-Saclay University), France, in 2013. Currently, he is a CNRS Research Director (Professor) and the Head of the Intelligent Physical Communications group in the Laboratory of Signals and Systems (L2S) at Paris-Saclay University – CNRS and CentraleSupélec, Paris, France. Also, he is an elected member of the L2S Board Council and a member of the L2S Management Committee, and is a Member of the Admission and Evaluation Committee of the Ph.D. School on Information and

Your opinion matters!

We created the following questionnaires through our LinkedIn Group:

- Optical wireless communications are taking their place in the 6G era, promising to enable a number of extra-ordinary applications, including nano-scale communications that can play a key role on countermeasure a number of diseases, implants in-body out-of-body communications, underwater high-data-rate communications, fronthaul communications, vehicle-to-everything communications, backhaul connectivity (Free space optics-FSO), as well as non-terrestrial and satellite communications. In your opinion, which is the most futuristic applications?
 - 50% of the participants answered nanoscale (in-body)
 - 25% of the participants went with underwater, and
 - 25% of the participants with non-terrestrial communications.

Communication Technologies, Paris-Saclay University. He is a Founding Member and the Academic Vice Chair of the Industry Specification Group (ISG) on Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) within the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), where he served as the Rapporteur for the work item on communication models, channel models, and evaluation methodologies. He is a Fellow of the IEEE, IET, EURASIP, and AAIA; an Academician of AIIA; an Ordinary Member of the European Academy of Sciences and Arts, an Ordinary Member of the Academia Europaea; an Ambassador of the European Association on Antennas and Propagation; and a Highly Cited Researcher. Also, he holds the 2023 France-Nokia Chair of Excellence in ICT, he holds the Tan Chin Tuan Exchange Fellowship in Engineering at Nanyang Technological University (Singapore), and he was a Fulbright Fellow at City University of New York (USA), a Nokia Foundation Visiting Professor (Finland), and a Royal Academy of Engineering Distinguished Visiting Fellow (UK). His recent research awards include the 2021 EURASIP Best Paper Award, the 2022 IEEE COMSOC Outstanding Paper Award, the 2022 Michel Monpetit Prize conferred by the French Academy of Sciences, the 2023 EURASIP Best Paper Award, the 2023 IEEE ICC Best Paper Award, the 2023 IEEE COMSOC Fred W. Ellersick Prize, the 2023 IEEE COMSOC Heinrich Hertz Award, the 2023 IEEE VTS James Evans Avant Garde Award, the 2023 IEEE COMSOC Technical Recognition Award from the Signal Processing and Computing for Communications Technical Committee, the 2024 IEEE COMSOC Fred W. Ellersick Prize, the 2024 Best Tutorial Paper Award, and the 2024 IEEE COMSOC Marconi Prize Paper Award in Wireless Communications. He served as the Editor-in-Chief of IEEE Communications Letters during the period 2019-2023, and he is now serving in the Advisory Board. He is currently serving as a Voting Member of the Fellow Evaluation Standing Committee and as the Director of Journals of the IEEE Communications Society.

The webinar had the following abstract: Next-generation wireless networks are expected to utilize the limited radio frequency (RF) resources more efficiently with the aid of intelligent transceivers and wireless environments. To this end, the concept of stacked intelligent metasurfaces (SIM) was born. A SIM is constructed by stacking an array of programmable metasurface layers, where each layer consists of a massive number of low-cost passive meta-atoms that individually manipulate the electromagnetic (EM) waves. By appropriately

Your opinion matters!

- Which do you believe is the key limited factor in optical wireless links?
 - 20% of the participants answered blockage
 - 67% of the participants voted misalignment & disorientation
 - 7% of the participants answered hardware imperfections, and
 - 7% of the participants voted for power limitations

Active questionnaires

The following questionnaire is still active in our LinkedIn Group:

- Which do you think is the order of data rate that a 1 km FSO link can achieve?
 - Mbps
 - Gbps
 - Tbps
 - Pbps

Do not miss the chance to cast your vote.

configuring the passive meta-atoms, an SIM is capable of accomplishing advanced computation and signal processing tasks, such as multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) precoding/combining, multi-user interference mitigation, and radar sensing, as the EM wave propagates through the multiple layers of the metasurface, which effectively reduces both the RF-related energy consumption and processing delay. Moreover, it is expected to become a key enabling technology for sensing in the wave domain.

In the webinar, there were more than 30 participants. The webinar was recorded and uploaded to YouTube.

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Prof. Marco Di Rezzo
Paris-Saclay University,
CNRS and Centrale Supélec

<https://zoom.us/my/uowm.ece1>

May 2024						
Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat
28	29	30	1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10	11
12	13	14	15	16	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25
26	27	28	29	30	31	1

Intelligent Metasurfaces: Reflecting & Refracting

The diagram illustrates a communication system using an intelligent metasurface. A Base Station (BS) on the left transmits an incident signal towards a central metasurface. The surface consists of a grid of elements, each containing a PIN diode, a ground plane, and a refractive/reflective patch. The surface can reflect the signal towards User 2 (labeled 'Reflected signal') or refract it towards User 1 (labeled 'Refractive signal'). An 'Energy Split' is shown between the two paths. The diagram also labels parameters G and H, and a phase shift ϕ .

Dissemination achievements

Till the fifth month of the project MINOAS, we achieved the following in terms of dissemination:

- MINOAS Website visitors > 1000
- YouTube channel viewers > 500
- YouTube channel videos = 15
- LinkedIn group members > 600
- Accepted journal papers = 2
- Preprints = 1
- Submitted conference papers = 1
- Patents filled = 3
- Keynote presentations = 2

Paper submission and preprint “On the Reliability and Security of Ambient Backscatter Uplink NOMA Networks”

The contribution was authored by Athanasios P. Chrysologou, Nestor D. Chatzidiamantis, Alexandros-Apostolos A. Boulogeorgos, Zhiguo Ding and it has the following abstract: A fundamental objective of the forthcoming sixth-generation wireless networks is to concurrently serve a vast array of devices many of which, such as Internet-of-Things (IoT) sensors, are projected to have low power requirements or even operate in a battery-free manner. To achieve this goal, non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) and ambient backscatter communications (AmBC) are regarded as two pivotal and promising technologies. In this work, we present a novel analytical framework for studying the reliability and security of uplink NOMA-based AmBC systems. Specifically, closed-form analytical expressions for both NOMA-users' and IoT backscatter device's (BD's) outage probabilities (OPs) are derived for both cases of perfect and imperfect successive interference cancellation (SIC). In addition, assuming that one NOMA-user transmits an artificial noise in order to enhance system's security, the physical layer security (PLS) of the system is investigated by extracting analytical expressions for NOMA-users' and BD's intercept probabilities (IPs). To gain insightful understandings, an asymptotic analysis is carried out by focusing on the high signal-to-noise (SNR) regime, which reveals that NOMA-users and BDs face outage floors in the high SNR regime as well as that IPs reach constant values at high SNR. Additionally, practical insights regarding how different system parameters affect these OP floors and IP constant values are extracted. Numerical results verify the accuracy of the developed theoretical framework, offer performance comparisons between the presented NOMA-based AmBC system and a conventional orthogonal multiple access-based AmBC system, and reveal the impact of different system parameters on the reliability and security of NOMA-based AmBC networks.

Get in touch with us

- Website: <https://minoas-project.gr/>
- YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@minoas-project>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/project-minoas/>
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61552919412515>
- Coordinator information:
Alexandros-Apostolos A. Boulogeorgos
(aboulogeorgos@uowm.gr)

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Keynote presentation in ICAETA 24

The MINOAS concept was presented in the 3rd international conference on advanced engineering, technology and applications (ICAETA 24). The conference was organized by the University of Catania that is located in Italy, and it was sponsored by the Istinye University, Iraqi Society for Engineering Management (ISEM), University of Anbar, and Ingenium Research Group.

The presentation title was “Towards intelligent optical wireless communication - The next gambit of the wireless world”. It was made by Prof. Boulogeorgos and it was organized in six parts. The first part introduced the audience in the new requirements of wireless world, the necessity to exploit the available resources in beyond mmWave bands, as well as in the applications of optical wireless communications in the sixth generation (6G) era. Next, the challenges of optical wireless communications was discussed followed by the MINOAS solution. The results of the first quarter of MINOAS was presented. Conclusions and round table discussion closed the keynote session.